

The Colour of Complex Diazoles.

Part I.

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1:2-Orthobenzoylene-1:3-benzdiazole is obtained in a good yield by the fusion together of phthalic anhydride and *o*-phenylene diamine (Bistrzycki and Lecco, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1921, 4, 425; compare also Thiele and Falk, *Annalen*, 1906, 347, 112; and Rupe and Thiess, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 4287). Bistrzycki and Lecco (*loc. cit.*) applied the same method to the condensation of *o*-phenylene diamine with tetrachlorophthalic acid, and with quinolinic acid. 1:2-*o*-Benzoylene-1:3-benzdiazole

has been recognised to be a powerful chromophore and contains a fused pyrrol-iminazole ring in its skeleton. Both the diazoles, tetrachloro-1:2-*o*-benzoylene-1:3-benzdiazole,

and 1:2-(α,β)-picolinoylene-1:3-benzdiazole,

contain the fused pyrrol-iminazole ring systems but whereas the former is coloured greenish-yellow the latter is absolutely colourless. This absence of colour in the picolinoylene compound may be due to the strong hypsochromic character of the pyridyl nitrogen atom (compare Ghosh, T., 1919, 115, 1103) which neutralises the chromophoric nature of the pyrrol-iminazole system. These important chromogenic properties of the fused heterocyclic system led the present author to investigate the properties of a series of analogous compounds which contained the pyridine-iminazole skeleton. With this view, as also with the object of studying the influence of additional fused ring systems on the depth of colour of these compounds, intermediates already containing fused rings such as 1:8-naphthalic anhydride and 1:2-naphthylene diamine have been employed in the condensation. Phthalic anhydride combines with 1:2-naphthylene diamine in alcoholic solution (compare Hans Lieb, Monatsh, 1918, 39, 873), to form 1':2'-naphthiminazole-2-phenyl-o-carboxylic acid,

which on treatment with acetic anhydride or on being heated to a high temperature loses a molecule of water and is converted into 1:2-o-benzoylene-1:3-naphthadiazole,

The latter crystallises in beautiful orange-yellow prisms. 1:2-(1':8')-Naphthoylene-1:3-benzdiazole,

derived from naphthalic anhydride and *o*-phenylene diamine has an intense yellow colour. 1;2-(1':8')-Naphthoylene-1:3-(2'') methylbenzdiazole

obtained from naphthalic anhydride and orthotoluylene diamine is coloured deeply yellow. The colour of 1:2-(1':8')-naphthoylene-1:3-(1'':2'')-naphthiminazole

obtained by the condensation of naphthalic anhydride with 1:2-naphthylene diamine is orange-red. All the compounds with formulæ III, IV and V contain a pyridine ring fused with an iminazole, one and all of them are intensely coloured. Thus like condensed pyrrol-iminazole ring systems, the pyridine-iminazoles also possess marked chromophoric properties. This is also borne out by the experiments of Bistrzycki and Fässler (*Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1923, 6, 519) who find that the compound obtained by the condensation of homophthalic anhydride with *o*-phenylene diamine is coloured.

1:2-Orthobenzoylene-1:3-(2'')-methyl-benzdiazole

obtained by the condensation of phthalic anhydride with 1:3:4-*o*-toluylene diamine is found to resemble 1:2-*o*-benzoylene-1:3-benzdiazole in colour. It thus appears that the effect of the presence of increasing fused ring systems is to deepen colour and that the naphthiminazoles

are generally more strongly coloured than the benzimidazoles. A comparison of colour of these compounds will make the point clear.

1 : 2-orthobenzoylene-1 : 3-benzdiazole	...	Yellow.
1 : 2-orthobenzoylene-1 : 3-methylbenzdiazole	...	Do.
1 : 2-o-benzoylene-1 : 3-naphthadiazole	...	Orange-yellow.
$\alpha\beta$ -diphenylacrylenebenzimidazole	...	Brown.
(Bistrzycki and Fässler, <i>loc. cit.</i>)		
O-phenyleneacetyl-2 : 1-benzimidazole	...	Yellow.
(Bistrzycki and Fässler, <i>loc. cit.</i>)		
Tetrachloro-1 : 2-o-benzoylene-1 : 3-benzdiazole	...	Greenish-yellow.
(Bistrzycki and Lecco)		
1 : 2-(1' : 8')-naphthoylene-1 : 3-benzdiazole	...	Deep yellow.
1 : 2-(1' : 8')-naphthoylene-1 : 3-methyl-benzdiazole		Do.
1 : 2-(1' : 8')-naphthoylene-1 : 3-naphthimidazole	...	Orange-red.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Phthalic Anhydride with 1 : 3 : 4-o-Tolylene Diamine. The Formation of Tolyleneamidine-benzenyl-o-carboxylic acid.—

Identical with the compound obtained by Bistrzycki (B: 23, 1042-1046) by the treatment of o-tolylene diamine with phthalaldehydic acid, is prepared by mixing together 3 gms. of the anhydride, 2.6 gms. of the diamine and 40 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The mixture is refluxed on the water bath for nearly 3 hours and allowed to cool. The residue is filtered off, washed with a little alcohol and ether and crystallised from 50% acetic acid. It has the melting point 260-262°. It is insoluble in water, chloroform, acetone, ether and toluene. It dissolves fairly in

mineral acids and also in alkalis and alkaline carbonates. (Found: C=71.18; H=4.51. $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_2$ requires C=71.43; H=4.76 per cent.).

1:2-Orthobenzoylene-1:3-methylbenzodiazole (VI).—The amidine carboxylic acid described above is heated in a dry tube when the diazole partly sublimes and condenses on the cooler part of the tube. This is scraped off and crystallised from absolute alcohol. The crystals are yellow and melt at 166°. They dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid giving a yellow solution with a green tint. (Found: C=76.75; H=4.50. $C_{15}H_{10}N_2O$ requires C=76.92; H=4.27 per cent.).

1':2'-Naphthiminazole-2-phenylorthocarboxylic Acid (I).—Lieb (*loc. cit.*) obtained this compound as a by-product during the preparation of diphtalyl-1:2-naphthylene diamine. But by boiling an absolute alcoholic solution of phthalic anhydride and 1:2-naphthylene diamine in equimolecular quantities for three to four hours, nearly a quantitative yield of the acid is obtained. The product of the reaction is cooled, the precipitate filtered off and repeatedly extracted with hot alcohol and acetone. The residue is then finally crystallised from nitrobenzene. The crystals melt above 300°. (Found: C=75.21; H=4.30. $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2$ requires C=75.00; H=4.16 per cent.).

Condensation of Naphthalic Anhydride with Orthophenylene diamine—the Formation of Orthoaminonaphthalanil:—

Three grams of the diamine are dissolved in 60 c.c. of absolute alcohol and five grams of naphthalic anhydride are then added to it. The mixture is then boiled under

reflux for 6—8 hours. On cooling the precipitate is filtered off and crystallised from acetone. The product is treated with sodium carbonate solution. The undissolved residue washed with hot water, melts at about 245° with decomposition with previous softening. (Found : C=74.92 ; H=4.25 ; N=9.57. $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2$ requires C=75.00 ; H=4.16 ; and N=9.72 per cent.). The alkaline extract on acidification with benzimidazole-2-naphthyl-8'-carboxylic acid yields silky needles of benzimidazole-2-naphthyl-8'-carboxylic acid melting at 265—269°.* (Found : N=9.61. $C_{18}H_{12}N_2O_2$ requires N=9.72 per cent.).

Acetyl Derivative.—The orthoaminonaphthalanil is dissolved in pyridine, acetyl chloride is added to it drop by drop and the mixture allowed to stand for about half an hour. On pouring the liquid into water and stirring with a glass rod the acetyl derivative solidifies. It is then crystallised from glacial acetic acid. It has the melting point 224°. (Found : C=72.50 ; H=4.63. $C_{20}H_{14}N_2O_2$ requires C=72.72 ; H=4.24 per cent.).

Benzoyl Derivative.—The orthoaminonaphthalanil is dissolved in pyridine and drop by drop an excess of benzoyl chloride added to the solution. It is allowed to stand for 10 minutes and a small quantity of hot water is added to it. The benzoyl derivative which crystallises out in yellow needles is recrystallised from pyridine and water. It melts at 209°. (Found : C=72.86 ; H=4.52 ; $C_{25}H_{18}N_2O_4$ requires C=73.17 ; H=4.40 per cent.).

N-Ethyl Derivative.—The orthoaminonaphthalanil is heated under reflux with excess of ethyl iodide for 6—8 hours. Then the excess of ethyl iodide is evaporated off and the product crystallised from alcohol. It melts at 235—37°. (Found : C=75.69 ; H=5.36. $C_{20}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires C=75.95 ; H=5.06 per cent.).

* All these compounds on heating are transformed into the corresponding diazoles. The melting points often are found to be not very sharp.

1 : 2·(1' : 8')-Naphthoylene-1 ; 3-benzdiazole (III).—

The orthoaminonaphthalanil or the benzimidazole-2-naphthyl-8'-carboxylic acid is heated at a temperature of 210—220° in an oil bath for about 2—3 hours. The substance gradually softens and finally becomes liquid. It is allowed to cool and extracted with absolute alcohol from which medium the diazole crystallises in deep yellow needles m. p. 198°. (Found: C=79·93; H=3·88. $C_{18}H_{10}N_2O$ requires C=80·00; H=3·70 per cent.). The same change occurs if either the anilide or the acid be boiled with acetic anhydride.

Condensation of Naphthalic Anhydride with Orthotoluylene Diamine.—4 gms. of naphthalic anhydride are mixed with 2·6 gms. of orthotoluylene diamine and 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol. The mixture is boiled on the water-bath for 6 hours. After allowing to cool the precipitate is filtered off and washed with a little alcohol. It is then extracted with boiling xylene. The xylene solution shows intense green fluorescence and on cooling deposits bright yellow crystals of orthoaminotolynaphthalimide,

m. p. 196°. (Found: C=75·31; H=4·52. $C_{19}H_{14}N_2O_2$ requires C=75·50; H=4·63 per cent.).

Toliminazole-2(1')-naphthyl-8'-carboxylic Acid,

The residue after extraction with xylene in the above experiment is dissolved in alkali, filtered and the solution neutralised with hydrochloric acid. The colourless crystalline product is filtered off, washed with water and dried. It melts at 273—75°. (Found: C=75·58; H=4·81. $C_{19}H_{14}N_2O_2$ requires C=75·50; H=4·63 per cent.).

1 : 2-(1' : 8')-Naphthoylene-1 : 3-methylbenzodiazole (IV).

—When the o-aminotolynaphthalimide is heated in a tube a deep yellow product boils over and condenses in the cooler part of the tube. The latter is crystallised from alcohol into deep yellow needles m. p. 187°. (Found : C=80·11 ; H=4·60. $C_{19}H_{12}N_2O$ requires C=80·28 ; H=4·22 per cent.).

Condensation of Naphthalic Anhydride and 1 : 2-Naphthylene Diamine—the Formation of 2'-Amino-N-(1')-naphthyl naphthalimide.—

Equimolecular quantities of the anhydride and the diamine are mixed with absolute alcohol and boiled for 10—12 hours. The brown precipitate is filtered off and extracted with alcohol, acetone and carbon bisulphide. The residue is finally crystallised from nitrobenzene. M. p. above 300°. (Found : C=77·79 ; H=3·98. $C_{22}H_{14}N_2O_2$ requires C=78·10 ; H=4·14 per cent.).

1 : 2-(1' : 8')-Naphthoylene-1 : 3-naphthiminazole (V).—The naphthalimide described above distills over on heating. The solid product is extracted with absolute alcohol which on cooling deposits beautiful orange-red crystals m. p. 256°. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid giving an yellow solution with intense green tint. (Found : C=82·24 ; H=4·51. $C_{22}H_{12}N_2O$ requires C=82·50 ; H=4·37 per cent.).

Further investigation to establish a relation between the colour and constitution of the diazoles is being carried on.

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